

Supplemental Material

The role of deep breaths in ultrasonic vocal production of Sprague Dawley rats.

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Rat	Total observation time (hours)	S	N	F	M
110	17	1	1	2	
111	35	1	3	4	2
136	13		1	2	
137	19	1	2	5	2
140	65		4	10	6
141	24	1	3	4	7
143	12	1	1	8	
144	19		1	3	4
145	38		2	2	1
151	22	1	1	6	1

Table S1: Total available time for each animal and number of successful recording sessions. S, sleep; N, mild noxious stimulus; F, female exposure; M, male exposure. S, N, F and M sessions lasted 20 minutes each. N, F and M sessions were preceded by a 10 minute resting period.